

ECONOMIC MECHANISM OF FORMATION AND USE OF LABOR FORCE IN THE RURAL AREAS

Yakupova A.N.

Nukus Innovation Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14266791>

The agricultural sector has significant potential for further growth, but unresolved systemic imbalances can restrain its development. Labor productivity in agricultural enterprises remains an acute problem for the economy of many countries. In modern market conditions, the management of ensuring the efficient operation of enterprises, increasing the level of profitability and competitiveness is possible only through the efficient use of labor resources. Today, there is a problem of devaluation of the labor force as the labor potential of sectors of the national economy.

The relevance of the work is due to the fact that the use of labor resources has recently become increasingly important, as well as the fact that the labor force has a cost estimate, economic and social guarantees of labor, on the one hand, and harsh conditions of labor activity - on the other, require deep analytical studies of the company's labor resources [1].

The agricultural sector of the economy is one of the most important spheres of material production, in which food products for the population and agricultural raw materials for industrial processing are produced. By the nature of the products manufactured, the agricultural sector belongs to the second division of social production of consumer goods (the first division of social production is represented by industries producing means of labor, in particular mechanical engineering, metallurgy, etc.).

The basis of the labor potential of the agricultural sector and the main object of the state's managerial influence is the rural population of working age. A necessary condition for the socio-economic development of agricultural production is the constancy of socio-demographic processes in the village. Labor resources are the main resource of each company, the quality and efficiency of which largely determine the company's performance and competitiveness. Labor resources provide movement to the material elements of production. Labor resources are a part of the working population that has the physical and mental abilities and knowledge necessary to carry out useful activities. The availability, sufficient quantity and quality of labor resources ensure efficient operation of the enterprise [2]. With the transition to a market economy, the analysis of labor relations becomes more significant, since the

labor force has a cost estimate and is competitive in the labor market. The growth of agricultural production can be achieved either by increasing the amount of resources used, or by improving the efficiency of their use. An important role in this regard is given to the rational use of labor resources. In order to improve the efficiency of the use of resource potential, the main directions of the formation of a system of effective management of the use and reproduction of the resource potential of the agricultural sector have been identified: ensuring the rational use of land, water and other natural resources in the agricultural sector, as well as basic material resources; the use of resource-saving technologies; efficient use of labor resources; ensuring the stability of the formation and efficiency of the use of internal and external financial resources; the introduction of the results of innovative development aimed at greening and intensifying agricultural production; development of transport and warehouse infrastructure; ensuring food security of the state.

The place and role of managing the introduction of labor resources is determined by the growing importance of the human factor in production, increasing the dependence of the results of companies on the quality, motivation and nature of the use of labor. The task of labor resource management is to study the qualitative aspects of employment, i.e. the compliance of a person's physical, professional and qualification abilities with the technical characteristics of the workplace and the functions it performs.

Conclusions. The formation of a market economy has a significant impact on the employment of the rural population. The guarantor of a stable life for peasants should be social measures that provide conditions for self-development and self-sufficiency of labor resources. At the same time, it is necessary to create material incentives, take into account the attitude to work and labor motivation. The state is an intermediary between the employer and the employee, determining the principles of coordinating the interests of these entities, creating conditions for the restoration of the labor force and forming the basis of the employment system. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the state adopts and implements legislative and regulatory acts governing the formation of effective employment of labor resources.

Literature:

1. Adamchuk V.V., Romanov O.V., Sorokina M.E. Economics and sociology of labor: a textbook for high school studentscall. - M.: Unity, 2000. - 407 p.
2. Aliev I.M., Gorelov N.A., Ilyina L.O. Labor Economics: a textbook for bachelors. - M.: Publishing house Yurait, 2013. - 671 p.

